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Sapere aude: Towards a brand new humanity

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Abstract

Knowledge that we possess nowadays circulates along a straight, and on an aligned path, despite of biotechnological and cybernetic advances. Showing clearly that we run quickly towards distant stars and transhumanism, but deep inside, we end up with an existential anguish from loss of meaning. Does science provides Human Beings freedom? Does it offer meanings for consciousness development?, or has become a new “myth” that, while it claims to explain how the world revolves, covers up a new mode of human manipulation?. Edward Matchett said: “Today it is easier to shout out loud Ahead than where to”.

Keywords: Consciousness; Crisis; Creativity; Humanity; Integration; Virus

1. Introduction

Sapere aude is a Latin expression meaning “dare you to know”; Also it is often interpreted as "dare you to think". Its disclosure at the end of the 18th century is due to Immanuel Kant philosopher, on his essay *Answered to the question: What is Enlightenment?* [1].

“Enlightenment is when a human being is liberated from his incapacity guilt. Incapacity is the impossibility of using our intelligence without guidance. Incapacity is the guilty one, because its cause does not reside on lack of intelligence but does resides on decisions and courage that we use without an influence or tutelage from another human being ;*Sapere aude!*...”

2. Nature and meaning of Human Existential Crisis

Currently true science revolution it is not about knowledge progress but is based on revolutionary thoughts (etymological sense of the term). It is not just about new ideas, but about a new thinking rhythm and it is this new rhythm that characterizes a new minded humanity. This change within " mind ecology" has been observed since the first third of the 20th century, while poets, philosophers and mystics anticipated a science and technology revolutionary movement; each one of these prophets draw a prefigurative sign that prepares the synthesis of thoughts of the 21st century. David Bohm, Ruper Sheldrake, James Lovelock, Ilya Prigogine, Edward Lorenz, John Bell, among others [2]. All these "revolutionaries" have something in common and that is why they try to unite what has been separated [3]. This does not mean that science is useless or that its possibilities have been terminated. Of course they are useful, but for applicative and practical purposes, but they are not useful to reveal to human beings the meaning of life and being within the universe.

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Every crisis not only marks the end of existence but opens a door to a new life dimension, although not everyone would like to cross that threshold. Nowadays, modern psychology has interest on existential crisis motivations discoveries and restoring the lost order, more than focusing on future messages that emerges behind a crisis. The subject is led to adapt onto a world that does not exist anymore for him, instead of helping him to face the fact that crisis brings new existential meanings. Therapy proposed an adaptation instead of a liberation path. Going back is impossible, once the old world has collapsed it is impossible to reoccupy an old space: either freedom is assumed or one will wander on a meaningless terrestrial aridity life... [4].

The transition from homo sapiens onto cosmic humans is imposed by irruption within human its elves and a new consciousness state [5,6]. It is a change caused by internal environment and the alternative is to transcend or die. The installation of this new medium within human physiology itself does not depend on political or social systems, but occurs as a concrete revelation act of consciousness. The existential crisis breaks the Being identification with the World. The World loses meaning and consciousness withdraws in on itself. We pass from an objective consciousness to consciousness without an object. The rupture of identification causes him anguish and he falls into an existential void, into an antimatter hole. Existential anguish (Being loneliness) should not be confused with pathological anguish (isolation solitude), is not a life death disease , it is not a pathological symptom that must be suppressed, but it is a sign of liberation that is to respect: An announce anguish, freedom that many human beings are afraid of ! and faced with a consciousness that has remained floating in thin air without an object, they prefer to fabricate an artificial goal rather than remain in that void waiting for a consciousness revelation; they rather return to that safety path that they have left behind, rather than exploring the uncertain future paths [7]. The existential crisis is a consciousness expansion, a release of energy. When consciousness detaches itself from its identification with to objects of the world and returns to itself, what is rescued in this reversion is not only an ideal, psychological or metaphysical consciousness, but is a quantum of energy, human energy that was linked to world objects, and free energy floods our organism, and we do not know what to do with it, which drives an existential anguish, its dramatic a vital character and it is not simply metaphysical. Therefore, it is not a great help for him to adapt to a world he has left behind, it is necessary to induce an awakening sense of creative action: not only to see the new world that opens before his eyes, but also to be encouraged to occupy it! [8].

This birth of a new inner liberation movement, is an existential joy, a transcendence joy of living, but a reversible transcendence: an awareness liberation and a willingness to participate. Individualism and socialism ends and a planetary community life begins. Einstein has already warned this well in advance when pointing out the close relationships between inductive physics, which is based on experimentation, and deductive physics, which starts from a prophetic intuition: the investigation of most of general laws by a state of consciousness that resembles religious or lovers [9]. When the will to know is placed at the service of consciousness being, thinking becomes feeling, reflection becomes comprehension, and dialectic becomes mystic. The human mystique is creating a brand new knowledge, When thoughts end, a new feeling is born. When mind is silent, the heart opens. New thoughts will flow from the heart. Eastern philosophies exalted the value of enlightened consciousness, while Western philosophy placed the accent onto will power, future human beings are building within themselves an instrument that articulates consciousness with will power, an organ that acts as a bridge between prophetic vision that anticipates the facts and an experience feeling which is based in facts. It is a new physiological relationship between the eye that reads a consciousness message and hands that translate into actions. The old man determines himself by means of fixed positions: ideological, dogmatic, scientific, social political positions, ... but we are no longer under a sign position (yoga or Egyptian art), but under life sign, and life is oscillation, pulse, alternative movement, rhythm, evolution and involution [10].

Eastern dilemma, posed in the Baghavad Gita between action and non-action is resolved, within history culture, a denial of the worlds philosophy and life [11]. Instead, the Bible points out another Western path. You will earn your bread with your effort. The first one is a consciousness expansion path the second one is an affirmation of a will power path. Which one will be the path for this new Era? What bread must I earn with my effort? Future man will not deny effort if he discovers a meaning for Being, but with lack of meaning there will be no effort and if that happens... and it is already happening, an ecological catastrophe would take place. The human path is something more than a method, is a living current technique, it has a pulse, breath, direction and meaning. It has place in space, time and beyond time, it has law, but there is something more than law. Communication is the paths meaning The place that each person occupies in the world becomes unique and significant. This is the sign that characterizes the brand new human path. Path itself has a meaning, a message, and a mission, is for future men to decipher the language path. Human path is not only means social communication nor pure cultural messages, but means an Union between invisible (spirit) and visible (matter). A bridge between divine and human. It is not traversed by imitation, but is discovered by similarity. The old paths are paths on stones, connections within space, terrestrial paths. Brand new paths are vibrational traces, tuned within time, cosmic paths. Meanings that structural units of a path, its cohesion, is not determined by a material form or by a social relationship, but by a spiritual bond. First of all we must understand, that the brand new path already exists, it already

vibrates in human beings and within the World. Vibrates with a different rhythm than those roads of the past. Vibratory jump, an environment change not only affects the rhythm of things, but also the rhythm of consciousness and life [5].

Transforming the dramatic existence of each one of us into an art work is the task before us: using old materials from our biography to produce a brand new life configuration. Revelation, together within history, art, philosophy and science, form the unity of knowledge. Actually, you don't have to go anywhere. Because the path is within me. For this recognition to occur, the mask of ego must fall and give way to soul forces (consciousness). This incorporation process is not governed by doctrine principles, by ceremonial formulas or by institutional forms, but by universal and sacred life laws. Human beings around the world, from different social and cultural conditions, are not only spiritual forces, but are also social fabrics, that invisible fabric that serves as physiological support for future humanity, where viruses, their components and regulators (prophages, proviruses) play a fundamental role in dynamics and evolutionary stability of living systems [12, 13, 14]. This is where these brand new human traits come from. If we search within ourselves, we carry the same heritage as the entire human race, good and bad, but we are unaware of that burden or aware of its consequences. The entire humanity is within me and even the smallest human being has a reality within me. Human society is an external reflection of who I am. What is outside is also inside. It is represented in our genes. In new generations, this feeling of organic solidarity, of awareness of belonging to a larger group, begins to take shape more clearly. Perception of total organism [4]. When I think and feel in terms of humanity, the vision of the world and life changes completely. And it changes, of course, the sense of responsibility of the individual being facing destiny of the human race [10]. I not only contributed by dirtying the atmosphere and contaminating the waters and the land, but also contributed by influencing the biological environment in which the heritage of humanity is shaped. This selfish individualism from the past gives way to a participation sense, not only social, but also a genetic participation, by offering life for a better future.

3. Creativity

Life is perceived by terms of work and performance. The obligation to act and life throttles are revealing themselves as an effective domination. Human existence is being absorbed by activity. Byung-Chul Han says that inactivity does not imply an activity incapacity or its rejection or its mere absence. It is a different intensity form that our society is not capable of perceiving. What makes authentically a human is the share of inactivity that is in it. Because inactivity is the true human form [15]. Remaining silent provides rich speeches, without silence there is no music, just noise. Where there is only stimulus-response, problem-solution, purpose-action scheme reigns, life degenerates only into survival. Life only gets its glow within inactivity, without the capacity for inactivity we become machines that just have to work. Today the free thinker is becoming extinct since there is no time to think, divergent opinions are no longer pondered, it is enough to hate them, says Nietzsche, anticipating our reality by more than a century ago [16]. Contemplative inactivity differentiates the thinker from the observer who always pursues a specific goal. The thinker has no purpose, he has no goal in mind. Knowledge fails to fully reflect life. Because known life is a dead life, the living is not transparent to itself. Not knowing how a form of inactivity revives life. Action is part of a story, but it is not a culture-forming force [15]. When fatigue accumulates in such a way that it is heavy, it makes it difficult for consciousness to intervene in daily activities, and it drives and automates us, like Sisyphus who was condemned to drag a huge stone to the top of a mountain. Each time he managed to reach the goal, the stone rolled back to the base, perpetuating Sisyphus's punishment and keeping him a slave to the promise of deliverance. He was condemned to do the same job without being able to finish it, without being able to connect with the key that could free him: his creativity. Creativity transforms the limited mind accustomed to a world of multiple new possibilities. The linear mind without creativity closes the door to the expression of human "inspiration" and reduces identity to the task it performs. The qualities and virtues of human potential are so immense and infinite, and creativity is such an accessible and buildable bridge for that potential to emerge in the world, that the mere fact of trying to be creative is already medicine for health. Plurality is so beautiful, as rich and prosperous as nature is, thousands of expressions of the same universal energy.

4. Creative relationship between tangible and invisible

What brings an excessive proliferation of materialistic life and a virus virulence? The information that has been left out of consciousness through biology. It incorporates in our physical body the information we have left in the shadow. This is it, it informs biology.

From the astrological analysis, when we do not take into account totality of what we are, everything that we do is not recognize as our own, remains in the shadow of our aura. When the time comes, that information, which must be incorporated, reaches us as destination. Such as a conflict situation, crisis, illness. These situations come to bring us information about ourselves.

Why is it like this? From tradition and sacred sciences, we are told that we are part of a unique totality, which manifests itself in thousands of aspects and forms in an evolutionary process of self-knowledge. This creative totality is, at the same time, a field and an adventurer of its own development path. Therefore, everything is part of this field and nothing can be eliminated or taken outside, simply because there is no outside. As the kabbalist maxim says regarding the first affirmation of existence: "All power that always was and will be is here and now" [17].

Every time we become polarized, which mean, every time we try to ignore part of who we are, the polarized reality or experience we have created takes us, through a crisis, to the other extreme until we manage to calibrate both extremes and integrate a brand new one. Or a more balanced reality.

As long as we remain within polarity, fighting to stop movement, identifying with one part, pretending to choose and ignoring this unified field in which we move and have our being, the Law of Polarity will lead us to experience the other extreme [18].

Key 11 of the Tarot, Justice, speaks of the Law. Especially the Law of Karma, understood as a principle of dynamic and harmonic balance, which releases overload and fills the gaps [19]. This key corresponds to the zodiac sign of Libra whose astrological ruler is the planet Venus. Mythologically, Venus is born from a whirlpool in the foam of the sea, the symbolic evocation of the golden spiral and the number phi, the divine proportion.

José Martínez Aroza, a mathematician from the University of Granada, Spain, in his article on "Fractal Art" talks about the impossibility of modifying the geometric image or drawing of a fractal equation. "Everything, absolutely everything that appears in each image, has emerged from a single equation. To such an extent that if the author of the equation does not like a part of the expressed image and wants to change it, then he must choose between leaving it as it is or changing it all, modifying his formula." [20, 21]. The harmonic balance sustains existence and that is what the Kabbalistic Tree of Life expresses.

In the founding myth of humanity, the myth of the fall, Adam and Eve are warned not to eat from the Knowledge tree, science, good and evil, a necessary evolutionary step to develop our intellect, our scientific/creative mind and our ability to conceptualize reality.

When Adam and Eve bite into the apple they become "conscious", they realize that they are naked and embody density. It begins to be governed by the purest laws of a physical world and biology; working the land to eat, giving birth in pain, interacting and understanding the order of the world of matter. We begin to experience Duality, with a consequent risk of polarizing ourselves and forgetting our Origins.

But that was the way. Who is the serpent that tempts Eve? Who are Adam and Eve? Who are they but the totality itself unfolding through its own logic, Intelligence of Creation unfolding with infinite Beauty and Wisdom.

We have eaten from the The knowledge tree and we have fed reason in an excessive way, we have confronted good and evil on a sterile fight, eating from the knowledge tree has made us forget the tree of life. By polarizing us, the darkened part of reality arrives, to restore the lost balance.

5. Conclusion

The cosmic human has already been born and we need science to help us to reveal all the keys to its development. We must learn to detect beings presence liberated next to us and to join them through similarity bonds. The theory about the brand new human phenomenon is no longer enough, testimony is needed. And this will to testify, which is, at the same time, a transcendence vocation and an inspiration source, is a vibratory note from future researchers, artists, scholars, teachers and students, they themselves operate as transistors between cosmic consciousness and human matter. Today is Time

Compliance with ethical standards

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The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential of interest.

Author Contributions

The authors have made a substantial direct and intellectual contribution to this work and approved it for publication. Each author contributed equally to all sections of the manuscript.

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